

Strengthening of Powdermetallurgically Produced Aluminum by Nanoscale Particles

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1 Introduction

The mechanical high temperature properties of commercial aluminum alloys are limited mainly due to their low melting temperatures and the related thermo-dynamical restrictions. Therefore the development of improved aluminum materials with high strength at elevated temperatures and sufficient ductility is still a big challenge for future energy saving applications especially for transport facilities.

Up to now there have been many scientific and technical attempts to overcome the thermo-dynamic restrictions like coarsening and dissolution of precipitates that appear in developing commercial temperature resistant aluminum alloys. One of them is the dispersion of ceramic particles into the metallic matrix. The dispersed particles must be stable in the target temperature range and they must stick in the metallic matrix.

Strength and hardness of metal-matrix-composites (MMCs) increase for homogeneously distributed and non sliceable particles with their mean distance due to the well known Orowan-process. This means that particles must be as small and as homogeneously distributed as possible in order to achieve maximum strength with a given volume fraction of particles. These particle strengthening fundamentals control the possible maximum increase of strength with dispersed particles. They are scientifically well investigated [1] and up to now many attempts have been undertaken to realize the necessary preparation conditions of according composites. Because nowadays a large variety of ultra-fine or even nano-scale ceramic powders is available the homogenous distribution of the ceramic particles is the main task that has to be solved.

For the present investigation, a powder metallurgical (PM) route using co ball milling of nano-scale ceramic and micro-scale aluminum (Al) powders was used to decrease the mean particle distance of ceramic dispersoids resulting in creep resistant Al MMCs with low particle volume fraction.

2 Experimental

2.1 Sample preparation

Al-matrix-composites containing nano-scale alumina (Al_2O_3) and/or boron nitride (BN) dispersoids were prepared by a PM route. Secondary powder suitable for further processing was produced by ball milling of water atomized Al powder (25 μm and 45 μm mean diameter, TLS Technik Spezialpulver, Bitterfeld, Germany) with various additions of the smaller hexagonal BN powders (500 nm mean diameter, Henze BNP GmbH, Kempten, Germany) and release agent zinc stearate (Baerlocher GmbH, Unterschleissheim, Germany) in a planetary ball mill under air atmosphere.

Ball milling was done in corundum-coated steel milling cylinders, 8 mm height and 10 mm diameter with 13 mm mean diameter corundum balls and various powder to ball mass ratios. Moreover the milling was done successively in three stages: In the first one with 120 Hz rotation frequency and 2 h duration the different primary powders were mainly homogeneously mixed. This means that the smaller BN particles are homogeneously dispersed over the surface of the bigger aluminum particles without plastic deformation.

In the second stage with 180 - 200 Hz rotation frequency and 2h duration the Al particles are plastically deformed and forged to bigger agglomerates wherein already some ceramic particles are dispersed. Due to this cold working and the increasing amount of ceramic particles these agglomerates repeatedly break apart and the BN- and or Al_2O_3 -particles enter into the surface regions of the plastically deformed agglomerates. Different to the BN-particles the Al_2O_3 -particles come from the oxide surface layers of the aluminium powder particles and the oxidized Al in the closed milling cup during milling. The volume fraction of Al_2O_3 for all ball milled materials is estimated to be about 0.9 vol. %.

In the third milling stage with 140 Hz rotation frequency and 2 h duration very big agglomerates are broken. This leads to a non-agglomerated secondary MMC-powder with flake like particles of about 20 μm diameter and 5 μm thickness that can be consolidated by hot extrusion. Because of this production process some alumina dispersoids are always present in the produced material which content can be controlled by the milling parameters. The contents of the various dispersoids and the varied milling parameters are given in tab. 1.

The ball milled (secondary MMC) powder was filled into Al capsules of 67 mm diameter, 2 mm wall thickness and about 250 mm height and multistage cold pre-pressed with maximum pressure of 65 MPa. Then they were hot extruded to rods of 12 mm diameter (3.4 extrusion ratio) at 350°C and an extrusion velocity of 2 mm/s after preheating for 3 h at the same temperature [2, 3]

2.2 Material characterization methods

Samples for tensile testing with 5 mm diameter and 56 mm active length were machined out of the hot extruded rods. Tensile testing was carried out at room temperature in an Instron 5582 universal mechanical testing machine.

Density measurements were performed on cylindrical samples 10 mm long which were machined to 8 mm diameter out of pieces cut from the extruded rods. Density was calculated from the samples weight in air and water using Archimedes' principle. The porosity of the samples was determined as the relative difference between the measured and the theoretical density.

Micro hardness measurements were performed using fully automatic micro hardness tester (Q10A, Quess GmbH, Golling, Austria). Test method and load application were Vickers HV0.05, DIN EN ISO 6507, with load time of 10 s.

Thermal conductivity was estimated from measurements of thermal diffusivity multiplied with specific heat capacity and density values [7, 8]. Diffusivity was measured with a laser flash method using Netzsch Microflash LFA 457 (Netzsch, Selb, Germany). The samples used for this measurement were 10 mm in diameter and 1 mm in thickness.

Samples for damping measurements, 2 mm thick, 10 mm wide, and 80 mm long with cylindrical strengthening of 10 mm diameter and 30 mm length at one side were machined out of the rods too. Strain amplitude dependent damping was determined by measuring the logarithmic decrement of freely decaying bending vibrations of the samples clamped at the strengthened end by the decaying amplitude of

vibration. For this the specimens were excited into resonance of the first fundamental bending frequency by a permanent magnet fixed at the free end of the bending beam and a sinusoidal alternating magnetic field. The resonant frequency of the vibrating arrangement ranged from about 30 to 40 Hz. Experimental details concerning damping measurements are explained in more detail in [2].

3 Results and discussion

Stress-strain-diagrams of the tensile tests at room temperature for hot extruded samples produced from Al powder, ball milled Al powder without additions, and ball milled Al powder with additions of 0.03 vol. % BN particles to Al powder, are shown in Fig. 1. It can be observed that ball milling with BN powder additions leads to a drastic increase of mainly the ductility of the material for both, hot extruded and heat treated material compared to samples without BN. Yield strength can be observed to be increased by BN too. The heat treatment for two hours at 450°C, which is 100°C above the hot extrusion temperature, causes a decrease of the yield tensile strength as well as an increase of the plasticity. This can be attributed to further recrystallization after incomplete dynamic recrystallization during hot extrusion. The lower ductility of the samples prepared from ball milled Al powder compared to equally treated samples from not milled powder is reasonable and can be attributed to high density of consolidation defects like coarse Al_2O_3 particles, agglomerates, and pores that originate during milling.

If only a small content of 0.03 vol. % BN is dispersed in MMC the, the situation considerably changes and materials show higher strength, higher ductility and negligible recrystallization after 2h heat treatment at 450°C. The reason for all this is not really clear and may be due caused by a better consolidation during hot extrusion due to easily sliceable BN particles. Another reason can be simply dispersion hardening due to dispersion with BN and/or Al_2O_3 particles. The very small difference between the tensile curves shown in Fig. 1c indicates effective suppression of recrystallization caused by the dispersed particles.

In Fig. 2 the results of the tensile tests for samples produced with different milling intensities (4:1 and 1:1 ball to powder ratios (BPR)) and different BN volume fractions (a) 0.3 vol. %, b) 0.8 vol. % BN) with and without heat treatment are compared. In all cases the ductility increases with increasing BN content. Further increases the tensile

strength with increasing milling intensity, while the development of the ductility is not uniform in all cases.

In Tab. 2 the mechanical properties evaluated from Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 are given. It is interesting to realize, that samples with 0.3 vol. % BN show a higher increase in strength if the corresponding secondary powder was milled with 4:1 BPR compared to 1:1 BPR which leads only to the half increase in strength. Moreover, a higher content of BN particles does not lead to such a high strength even if a milling intensity of 4:1 BPR is used. This clearly indicates that the milling parameters are much more important for the strength increase than the BN content. This behavior is consistent with the Orowan theory that dislocations circumvent small particles instead of cutting them. In this case the strengthening by particles mainly depends on the free distance between the dispersoids L like

$$\Delta\tau_p = \alpha(Gb/L) \quad (1)$$

where G is shear modulus of the dislocations glide system of the, b is the length of the burgers vector and α is a proportional factor depending on the arrangement of dislocations. Equation 1 gives the maximum strength for with similar inter particle distances. For these dispersoids, acting as non-sliceable obstacles particles must be homogeneously distributed. Due to geometrical reasons the free distance between dispersoids is connected with its diameter d and volume fraction f . The following equation holds for small (about less than 10 vol. %) particle volume fractions.

$$L \approx d/\sqrt{f} \quad (2)$$

and therefore the maximum expectable strength increase by dispersed particles is about

$$\Delta\tau_p \approx \alpha Gb(\sqrt{f}/d) \quad (3)$$

Assuming the volume fraction of dispersoids is 1 %, and $\alpha \approx 1$, a simple estimation with equation (3) leads to a stress increase in the order of 50-100 MPa if the particle's diameter is assumed to be about 100 nm. This shows, that the responsible particles for dispersion strengthening (Al_2O_3 and/or BN) must be very small, nearly homogeneously distributed, and the material with 0.3 vol % BN is nearly optimum strengthened. This also implies that the primary particles in the hardly milled material have been seriously grinded down during ball milling.

For 0.3 vol. % BN and for 0.8 vol. % BN additions the heat treatment (450°C, 2 h) does not change the tensile yield strength. This indicates that other strengthening mechanisms like grain hardening or cold working don't play a role in the improvement of strength. The decrease of the ductility of most specimens is not fully understood up to now. This may be due to debinding of dispersoids from the aluminum matrix but also individual macroscopic differences between the single samples may play a role.

The thermal conductivity of aluminum is isotropic. Literature gives a value of $280 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ for Al 99,8 [5]. The thermal conductivity of BN is strongly anisotropic. It ranges from $2 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ in the basal plane to $400 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ perpendicular to it [6]. Due to this strong anisotropy and the unknown texture of our tests materials, the thermal conductivities (Fig. 3) of the resulting composites can not be calculated in a reasonable way. Moreover the changes of the thermal conductivity with the BN volume fraction in the investigated range are small as can be expected by the uniformly small contents. Nevertheless the decrease of the thermal conductivity with the BN volume fraction is not monotonous. This finding must be attributed to contrary effects of changing texture and/or consolidation success with BN content. Up to now these effects could not be separated by density measurements because the densities of BN (2.25 g/cm^3) and Al (2.70 g/cm^3) are too similar and the BN content was too low. The measured densities of the investigated samples ranged in the very small interval from 2.69 to 2.70 g/cm^3 .

Strain amplitude dependent damping measurements displayed in Fig. 4 show typical dislocation damping behavior. With increasing strain amplitude the damping increases too in a manner similar to results first fully explained by the theory of Granato and Lücke (GL) [9, 10]. The measurements confirm the results found for the mechanical properties. Dislocation damping is highest for the samples which were hot extruded from unmilled Al powder. Also the ageing of damping is much higher compared to material hot extruded from powder co milled (4:1 BPR) with 0.3 vol. % BN. Small deviations from GL behavior can be observed in the course of the damping versus strain amplitude curves. The knee in Fig. 4b) may be due to additional damping mechanisms due to the dispersed BN and/or Al_2O_3 particles.

4 Conclusion

The experiments show that the milling parameters are crucial for the mechanical properties of the Al-BN-Al₂O₃ composite. With intensity of milling the tensile strength increases much more than with volume fraction of BN. This strong increase can be explained by the Orowan mechanism. For special parameters it could be estimated that the Orowan process could be nearly totally utilized. The most effective dispersoids, BN or Al₂O₃, could not definitely be identified in this contribution but the BN content is important at least for the dispersion process during intensive ball milling. A previous publication [4] favours BN to be the most effective one.

The intensities of damping as well as the ageing results of damping confirm the dislocations to be pinned by BN and/or Al₂O₃ particles.

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Tab. 1. Dispersoid content in Al-Matrix and ball to powder mass ratio of the investigated samples. Al₂O₃ content of all samples is estimated to be 0.9 vol. %.

Name of sample	Ratio ball : powder	BN particles in Al-Matrix in vol.%
Al	-	-
Al-1	1:1	0.00
0.03BN-1	1:1	0.03
0.3BN-1	1:1	0.30
0.8BN-1	1:1	0.80
0.3BN-4	4:1	0.30
0.8BN-4	4:1	0.80

Fig. 1. Tensile tests performed at room temperature with $3.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$ strain rate for hot extruded samples of a) Al, b) Al ball milled, and c) 0.03BN-1, Al with 0.03 vol. % BN ball milled. For b) and c) ball milling was done with ball to powder ratio 1:1. Black curves – as hot extruded, red curves – heat treated 2h at 450°C.

Tab. 2. Mechanical properties at room temperature obtained from the tensile tests shown in Figs. 1 and 2

Name of sample	Mechanical property in MPa			
	$\sigma_{p0.2}$	$\sigma_{p0.2}$ 2h 450°C	σ_m	σ_m 2h 450°C
Al-1	88	87	130	125
0.03BN-1	98	91	135	140
0.8BN-1	96	86	145	155
0.3BN-4	246	216	266	285
0.8BN-4	80	70	150	210

Tab. 3. Vickers Hardness of investigated samples

Name of sample	HV0.05	
	after hot extrusion	after 2h at 450°C
Al -1	33	35
0.03BN-1	35	37
0.3BN-4	71	-
0.8BN-1	38	40
0.8BN-4	48	-

Fig. 2. Tensile tests at room temperature performed with a strain rate of $3.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$ for milled powders with ball to powder of ratio 1:1, black curves – as hot extruded, red curves – heat treated 2h at 450°C or 4:1, blue curves – as hot extruded, violet curves – heat treated 2h at 450°C and hot extruded at 350°C a) 0.3BN-1 and 0.3BN-4, Al with 0.3 vol.% BN, b) 0.8BN-1 and 0.8BN-4, Al with 0.8 vol.% BN

Fig. 3. Temperature dependence of thermal conductivity of powders hot extruded at 350°C. Not milled Al powder (closed symbol). Ball milled powder with ball to powder ratio 1:1 and 0.03, 0.3, 0.8 vol.% BN (open symbols). Blue symbol (closed circles): Literature values of Al [5]

Fig. 4. Damping as log. decrement of freely decaying bending beam vibration versus maximum strain amplitude in bending beam in log. scale of samples a) Al, b) 0.3BN-4, Al with 0.3 vol. % BN. Closed black squares – hot extruded at 350°C, closed red circles – heat treated at 350°C 1h, open triangles on bottom – aged for 1d at RT, open triangles on top - aged for a) 3d and b) 7d, at RT